

LEARNING STYLES

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Anontatsiya: Ushbu maqolada odamlarni tashqi malumotlarni o'zlashtirishi o'rganish va qabul qilish to'g'risida so'z yuritiladi.

Annotation: This article discusses how people learn and accept external information.

Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждается, как люди узнают и принимают внешнюю информацию.

Key words: Learning style, visual learning style, auditory learning style, kinesthetic learning style, tactile learning style, listening learning style, read and write learning style.

A learning style is the way that different students learn. A style of learning refers to an individual's preferred way to absorb, process, comprehend and retain information. The four key learning styles are: visual, auditory, tactile and kinaesthetic.

The auditory learning style

Identifying your learning style involves understanding how you tend to learn best. You can use this information to your advantage when you study by using learning approaches that work well for you, such as writing out notes, creating mind-maps, using models or reciting out loud. The auditory learning style means a person learns best by listening. Music, video clips and conversations are their ideal way of learning. Auditory learners tend to do well in a traditional school environment listening to lectures, and also contributing to discussions.

Auditory learners learn through listening. As such, attending lectures, tutorials, and group discussions are absolutely essential for these learners (it's also essential for the rest of us, being a read/write learner is no reason to skip lecture!). If you're an auditory learner, help yourself focus on text book readings by reading them out loud, so you can hear how the words sound. It can also be really helpful to engage in group discussions about course concepts and topics—create a weekly study group to get together weekly just to talk about the things being discussed in lectures. Leave lots of extra room on your page when taking notes in lectures, and then return to these notes after you've had a chance to discuss the material in further detail—supplement with the new information you have.

Visual learning style.

Understanding learning styles can make it easier to create, modify, and develop more efficient curriculum and educational programs. It can also encourage students' participation in these programs and motivate them to gain professional knowledge. Visual learners are the most common type of learner, making up 65% of our population. Visual learners relate best to written information, notes, diagrams, and pictures.

Visual learners learn through seeing, so tools like diagrams, flowcharts, pictures and symbols can be key to understanding new concepts. As University style lectures tend to neglect visual components, it may be difficult for you visual learners out there to stay focused during a long lecture. When taking notes in class, something to try is developing a system of symbols to replace the written word. For example, instead of writing out “female” each time in your notes, simply use the standard symbol. Or instead of writing that the results of a particular test were positive, insert a smiley face! For visual learners, it is often far easier for recall to work with images as oppose to working with words, as you will picture the image in your head while recalling it—far more difficult when trying to recall the word itself! Other tricks to try for visual learners include spatially rearranging your page—instead of writing across a page horizontally, write in a way that is more descriptive of the relationship being described—for example, write the words out in a circular pattern if that more truly represents the relationship you are describing. Also, it can be useful to colour code your notes, to create more visual stimulation.

Kinesthetic learning style

Generally, students tend to favor one learning style more than another, but most people are a mix of two or maybe even three different styles. So, teachers, make sure you're creating a classroom that can engage any type of learner. This is the least common type of learner - - only around 5% of the population is a true kinesthetic learner. These individuals need to move, touch, feel, hold, and get active

Kinaesthetic Learners learn through doing. This is perhaps the most challenging learning style for university students, as there are not always style for university students, as there are not always many opportunities to engage in hand many opportunities to engage in hands on learning in lectures. For this reason, labs and tutorials become even more essential for these learners. While studying, try to incorporate all of your senses into the experience—the more of this

you can do, the higher your recall will be, as you'll have multiple cues. One way to create more useful study notes if you're a kinaesthetic learner is to fill your notes with several examples for each concept. Try taking an example from the text, or lecture, or lab, and then try creating your own example. As a general rule, the more personal your created example is, the better your recall will be for that example—and hopefully for the concept it is describing! Also try to make as much use of practise questions and exams as possible.

Read and write learning style

Read/write learners learn through—what else?—reading and writing. As such, university style courses suit these types of learners fairly well—plenty of text books and study notes to read. If you're a read/write learner, pay special attention to text book glossaries—better yet, make your own as you progress through a course. After lecture, return to your notes for review, read them over, and then create a new, condensed set of study notes. Lists can also be a very useful tool. And a good tip for all students is to rewrite explanation and notes out into your own words.

If you can't rewrite a definition or describe a concept in your own words, concisely, there is a good chance that there is an aspect of that concept that you don't fully understand. Return to this concept for further review.

Although many of us remain fairly constant in our learning preference throughout time, styles can and do change with some regularity—this can be influenced by your learning styles can and do change with some regularity—this can be influenced by your learning environment—perhaps after several years at university you'll discover that you have become more of a read/write learner than you were in high school. For this reason, it can be a good idea to retake the VARK annually to ensure that you're using study methods that best suit your current learning needs. In addition, when you take the VARK, you will notice that you will most likely have a preference for one type of learning, although you will also respond positively for other styles as well (for example, you may predominantly be a visual learner, with a VARK score of 7, although you also show tendencies for read/write learning with a score of 5). Yet another possibility is that of the multimodal learner. You are a multimodal learner if you display two or more equally or near equally predominant learning preferences. Although it may seem desirable, now that you can easily find out what your learning style is, to only use study methods that seem to match with your style, this is not the best option. Instead, in each learner style there are great study strategies for all learners—so if you're an auditory learner, take some tips from your kinaesthetic friends and add even more examples into your study notes

References: Google website, wisdom book, learning styles book and etc.